

Data Management Plan (updated version)

Deliverable D7.9

Release Status: Public

Author: Romain F H Viguier, SCCS

Date: 21 June 2024

Filename and Version: PilotSTRATEGY_Data_Management_Plan_Initial_D7.9_V04

Project ID Number: 101022664

PilotSTRATEGY (H2020- Topic LC-SC3-NZE-6-2020 - RIA)

[@pilotstrategy](https://twitter.com/pilotstrategy)

www.pilotstrategy.eu

Document History

Location

This document is stored in the following location:

Filename	PilotSTRATEGY_Data_Management_Plan_updated_D7.9_V04
Location	

Revision History

This document has been through the following revisions:

Versi on No.	Revision Date	Filename/Location stored:	Brief Summary of Changes
V01	15 Oct 21	PilotSTRATEGY_Data_Management_Plan_Initial_D7.9_V01	First draft
V02	01 Nov 21	PilotSTRATEGY_Data_Management_Plan_Initial_D7.9_V02	Feedback and comments from partners
V03	24 Apr 24	PilotSTRATEGY_Data_Management_Plan_updated_D7.9_V03	Updates on Metadata
V04	10 Jun 24	PilotSTRATEGY_Data_Management_Plan_updated_D7.9_V04	Added info regarding Repository

Authorisation

This document requires the following approvals:

AUTHORISATION	Name	Signature	Date
WP 7 Leader	Romain F H Viguier		21/06/24
Project Coordinator	Isaline Gravaud		27/06/24

Distribution

This document has been distributed to:

Name	Title	Version Issued	Date of Issue
			00/00/0000

--	--	--	--

© European Union, 2024

No third-party textual or artistic material is included in the publication without the copyright holder's prior consent to further dissemination by other third parties.

Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Disclaimer

The information and views set out in this document are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and

bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Executive summary

The objective of the Data Management Plan (DMP) is to identify the data used and generated in the project and to outline how this data will be made findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, in accordance with the principles of FAIR data management. This document adheres to the European Commission's guidelines on FAIR data management in Horizon 2020 (version 3.0, 26th July 2016) and provides information about the collected data, including its purpose, utility, accessibility, and reusability.

This is an updated version of the project's DMP and includes the selection of a repository for long-term data storage. The DMP will be continuously reviewed, updated, and completed throughout the project, with the final version constituting the project's Final DMP (deliverable D7.10).

Table of Contents

Document History	1
Location	1
Revision History	1
Authorisation	1
Distribution	1
Executive summary	4
Table of Contents	5
1. Introduction	7
2. Data Summary	7
2.1 Purpose of the data collection/generation	7
2.2 Types and formats of data generated/collected	8
2.3 Data utility	9
3. FAIR data	9
Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	9
Metadata.....	9
3.1.1 Digital object identifiers (DOIs)	10
3.1.2 Data access statement	11
3.2 Making data openly accessible	11
3.3 Categorisation of data access	11
3.4 Data access committee	12
4. Allocation of resources	12
5. Data security	12
6. Ethical aspects	13
7. PilotSTRATEGY data repository	13
7.1 PilotSTRATEGY community 13	
7.2 Step per step guide on Zenodo	13
7.3 Metadata for Zenodo	13

8. Resources for DMP development	13
ANNEX 1 - DATA QUESTIONNAIRE	15

1. Introduction

Research data management in project PilotSTRATEGY will follow the Horizon 2020 program's guidelines on FAIR data management and shall be governed by Article 29 (Dissemination of results – open access – visibility of EU funding) of the Grant Agreement.

The dissemination of project PilotSTRATEGY data is subject to a procedure for dissemination approval that is stated in Article 8.4 (Dissemination) of the Consortium Agreement.

The Data Management Plan will describe the research data used and generated by the project and will ensure that research data are findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable. The DMP is established in collaboration with all partners in agreement with the dissemination requirement stated in the Grant agreement and with the procedure for dissemination approval stated in the consortium agreement.

The WP7 leader, SCCS/UEDIN is responsible for the coordination of task 7.6 (Data Management Plan) which includes:

- The selection of a repository for project data to provide open access to publications and data generated by the project
- Preparation of rules and instructions for data deposition in the project
- Preparation and annual update of the DMP

The project has constituted five local teams, which are groups of partners from a specific region, in charge of conducting the main work in their area. Local teams are composed of one or more institutions and are coordinated by a Public Organisation that will ensure project outputs are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR).

These Public Organizations are:

- BRGM for the Paris-Orléans area
- IGME for the Ebro Basin
- UEVORA for the Lusitanian Basin
- CERTH for the West Macedonia area
- GIG for the Upper Silesia area

2. Data Summary

2.1 Purpose of the data collection/generation

PilotSTRATEGY project is investigating geological CO₂ storage sites in industrial regions of Southern and Eastern Europe for the purpose of large-scale carbon capture and storage (CCS) development.

Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) has a crucial role in Europe's climate ambitions, particularly for the future viability of industrialised regions. Meeting the challenge will depend on the right amount of geological CO₂ storage becoming available in time. PilotSTRATEGY aims to add CCS to the feasible climate mitigation options available to local industries and communities.

Storage pilots will help us develop Europe's CO₂ storage capacity and build confidence in CCS. PilotSTRATEGY will provide the technical basis for the implementation of pilot storage sites in five target regions, with a focus on deep saline aquifers, a largely untapped storage resource.

The project will assess factors such as a storage site's integrity, capacity, hydrodynamics, and monitoring options and undertake research into stakeholder engagement, including an evaluation of factors that affect CCS acceptance.

The project research focussing on the Paris, Lusitanian, and Ebro basins will;

- provide 3D characterisation of storage sites and storage complexes, including sedimentology, structural geology, initial field stress and natural seismicity
- establish an injection strategy and an assessment of CO₂ behaviour in the long term
- provide detailed Measurement, Monitoring and Verification (MMV) strategies as well as plans for preventive and corrective measures
- carry out pre-FEED studies for CO₂ storage resources based on pre-feasibility studies from the STRATEGY CCUS project
- involve regional stakeholders in the pilot's conceptualisation, design and monitoring strategies development
- develop recommendations for stakeholder and public participation in the delivery of geological CO₂ storage pilots

The project research focussing on West Macedonia and Upper Silesia will;

- enhance understanding of CO₂ storage resources by studying new data, reprocessing current data and conducting new dynamic simulation studies
- allow these resources to be part of contingency storage planning for the regions
- involve regional stakeholders, including communities and the wider public, in CCUS public engagement studies

2.2 Types and formats of data generated/collected

Different types and formats of data will be collected and generated in project PilotSTRATEGY.

Data from experimental and modelling work will be generated in technical work-packages (WP2-WP5) in the lab and from field experiments.

Qualitative and quantitative data will be generated through interviews, questionnaires, and workshops by human science related activities (WP6). This data will be anonymised and processed in the project. The questionnaire in annex 1 will help gather all information related to types and formats of generated /collected data.

All information related to types and formats of generated /collected data is collected using a questionnaire. This questionnaire is transmitted via the WP leaders and filled by the partners. Completed questionnaires are uploaded on the project Sharepoint.

The data questionnaire has been updated to tackle metadata (see **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**) and is joint in Annex 1. Collection of project data will be updated and listed in a main table.

2.3 Data utility

The data collected and generated in the PilotSTRATEGY project will be useful for different groups of stakeholders:

- Research institutes, universities, other R&D organisations active in CO₂ storage assessment or appraisal will use the data to inform, educate and further research work
- Municipalities, Local authorities, NGO, decision makers will use the data to support decisions to be made regarding the development of CO₂ store in Deep Aquifer.
- CCUS developers, geological CO₂ storage pilot operators, will use the data to develop further CO₂ stores, to plan future CCUS infrastructure.

3. FAIR data

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Data should be discoverable, with fully searchable metadata to inform prospective users of the data prepared to recognised data management standards and published in data repositories.

A listing of datasets will be maintained on the PilotSTRATEGY website with links to the data, giving a central source of information describing data associated with the project. This will be coordinated between the data manager and the project dissemination team at the University of Edinburgh. Release of datasets will be made publicly known through the project website and social media accounts.

3.1.1 Metadata

Metadata is high level data that provides a brief summary of something, so that it can be easily catalogued and searched for.

Metadata includes a data title and a data description.

Data title: The data title should employ commonly used terms related to the dataset. It should succinctly convey the content of the dataset.

Data Description: The data description should offer a concise overview of the dataset's content, of 4000 characters maximum (but could be much shorter) aiding in determining its relevance. Most key information should be included in the first one or two sentences as they tend to be used by research engines. It may include references to publicly available papers or reports that elucidate the dataset or provide useful links to webpages.

Partners completing metadata should ensure that this is of high-quality enabling users in future to find a dataset and determine if they wish to use it. Metadata must include a good explanatory title and an accurate concise description (e.g. what, where, when, how, why, who).

What: Provides a concise description of what has been recorded and the format of the data. It aims to immediately inform the reader about the nature of the resource.

Where: Indicate the spatial coverage of the data.

When: The timeframe during which the data was collected, providing clarity on the temporal scope of the dataset.

How: A brief overview of the methodology used in data collection.

Why: The purpose behind data collection and the potential users who may find the data valuable.

Who: The parties responsible for collecting and interpreting the data are identified in this section.

Datasets generated will be INSPIRE compliant, with full metadata conforming to Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and DOI (Digital Object Identifiers) where appropriate. Metadata containing details of the dataset will be captured in a standardised discovery metadata format which complies with ISO standard 19115.

The Research Data Alliance provides a [Metadata Standards Directory](#)

(<http://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/>)

3.1.2 Digital object identifiers (DOIs)

It is recommended that Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) are applied to archived datasets where appropriate to enable citation of the information, particularly when data are referenced in a publication. This is a pre-requisite of leading science journals.

The DOI:

- allows data to be cited in the same manner as a scientific journal article
- enables credit to be assigned the dataset creators
- recognises the value of the data
- and the effort that has gone into its creation
- ensures the discoverability, permanence, and stability of the dataset

A DOI can be assigned before the dataset is released so that it can be referenced in the associated publication and the dataset can be released, when notified, at the same time as the publication. Datasets can be cross-linked back to the article.

Data can be archived without a DOI as not all data are appropriate for a DOI. For a dataset to be assigned a DOI, it must be provided to the data repository in good condition, with appropriate metadata and of a suitable level of technical quality. The data depository will be responsible for ensuring the data meets the required level of quality.

A DOI gives assurance to future users that the dataset is:

- Stable
- Complete
- Permanent
- Of good technical quality

The data repository is giving its stamp of approval, saying that the dataset is complete and that all the necessary metadata are available.

3.1.3 Data access statement

Partners must include a statement in their publication(s) describing how to access the data (or a statement explaining why access to underlying data has been restricted). If data are openly available, the name(s) of the data repositories should be provided, as well as any persistent identifiers (e.g. DOI) for the dataset.

3.2 Making data openly accessible

Due to the high level of public and industry interest in the potential impacts of CCS, the default position for the project will be for all finalised datasets to be open access. It is a requirement that all open data are accessible for the long-term. This makes the research process more robust by enabling validation of results and maximising the value obtained from publicly funded data. All public (written) deliverables should also be archived.

Data should be archived as open access which:

- underpins a publication
- has long-term interest with potential for re-use (including currently unforeseen uses)
- validates research findings
- is worth keeping

Benefits of open access:

- Accelerations of the research and discovery process
- Avoidance of the duplication of research efforts
- Enhanced opportunities for collaborations
- Broader and faster opportunities for the adoption and commercialisation of research findings

3.3 Categorisation of data access

However, not all data generated by PilotSTRATEGY must be open. The need to balance openness and protection of scientific/commercial information should be considered and certain datasets may need to remain closed according to the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary".

Project datasets should therefore be categorised. It should be carefully considered which data can be made public (open access) from the onset, which should be placed under temporary embargo (< 2 years) before open release, and which must remain confidential. WP leaders should discuss with their work package participants/task leaders to determine this.

3.4 Data access committee

There is not a need for a separate data access committee, but this will be an item for discussion on Project Management Board meetings.

Examples of data which could be closed or restricted:

- Confidential information
- External industry data
- Commercial sensitivity/interest (e.g. new tools being developed with potential for patenting)
- Data with IPR issues
- Sensitive data containing personal information

Participant consent may also need to be obtained. This should be agreed during early stages of the project.

IPR and innovation for the project should be considered to ensure there are no conflicts between data sharing and these.

If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions) the restrictions associated with the data must be valid/reasonable. Metadata should include a statement specifying any restrictions.

For confidential data, it is recommended that a discovery metadata record is published to signpost that the data exists without necessarily archiving the data. This should contain a brief description, which directs any potential user to the data owner contact if more information is required or to discuss the possibility of data access, which could lead to future collaborations. It should be discussed with the participants if they wish to advertise their (confidential) data in this way or if they prefer to make no information available in some cases.

4. Allocation of resources

Data management costs are covered as part of the grant. WP7 lead will cover data manager role and identify repository to ensure long-term data management complies with current best practice to allow continuous data availability.

Beyond the end of the project, data archived in the repositories will be preserved and maintained for the long-term using the data repository resources. The costs associated with this will not be substantial.

5. Data security

Sensitive data should be encrypted when transferring.

6. Ethical aspects

All data must conform to the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) when personal information is involved. Data can be anonymised if needed.

There may be sensitivities with some data which means it is unsuitable for sharing. This should be decided by the data generator in discussion with the WP lead and the project Coordinator.

7. PilotSTRATEGY data repository

The project has selected Zenodo as a repository for project data, to provide open access to publications and to increase the visibility of data generated by the project.

7.1 PilotSTRATEGY community

The project has created a community on Zenodo. The link to the Zenodo community is <https://zenodo.org/communities/pilotstrategy>

7.2 Step per step guide on Zenodo

To help you get started, here's a step-by-step guide on how to upload to Zenodo: <https://help.zenodo.org/docs/deposit/create-new-upload/>

7.3 Metadata for Zenodo

Each data set and project deliverable uploaded to Zenodo must be accompanied by metadata, including the title, description, and keywords. Please refer to **Part 3 of the current document** on making your data FAIR, which covers the use of metadata.

8. Resources for DMP development

The Research Data Alliance provides a [Metadata Standards Directory](#) that can be searched for discipline-specific standards and associated tools.

The [EUDAT B2SHARE](#) tool includes a built-in license wizard that facilitates the selection of an adequate license for research data.

Useful listings of repositories include:

[Registry of Research Data Repositories](#)

Some repositories like [Zenodo](#), an OpenAIRE and CERN collaboration), allow researchers to deposit both publications and data, while providing tools to link them.

Other useful tools include [DMP online](#) and platforms for making individual scientific observations available such as [ScienceMatters](#)

ANNEX 1 - DATA QUESTIONNAIRE

To refine further the PilotSTRATEGY data management plan, it would assist if you could complete this questionnaire and upload it to the project SharePoint, in the following file:

[Documents/WP7-Communication/Data_Management_Plan/](#)

This will help identify and categorise project data and any potential problem areas.

1	Work package			
2	Task			
3	Contacts			
	Name			
	Organisation			
	e-mail			
4	Project timescale of data collection/production, from		to	
	Project timescale of data collection/production, from		to	
5	Where will you deposit data for long-term archiving?			
6	When do you expect to deposit data?			
7	Specific datasets			
8	All data will not necessarily be appropriate for long-term preservation with a data repository. Which of the above datasets may not be appropriate to deposit?			
9	Will you be providing any software? If yes, please provide more details Are there likely to be any licensing requirement?			
10	Are you using any existing data from project partners? If yes, please provide some details			

11 Are you using any external third-party data?

If yes, please provide some details

12 Does data require an embargo before open access release?

If yes, please provide some details

13 Is any data confidential or restricted?

If yes, please provide some details

14 Are there any intellectual property rights or commercial sensitivity issues that will restrict access to data?

If yes, please provide some details

15 Making data findable, including the provision for Metadata.

Metadata is high level data that provides a brief summary of something, so that it can be easily catalogued and searched for. **Metadata** includes a data title, a data description and a set of Keywords.

Data title:

Please propose a data title. The data title should employ commonly used terms related to the dataset. It should succinctly convey the content of the dataset.

Data Description:

The data description should offer a concise overview of the dataset's content, of 4000 characters maximum (but could be much shorter) aiding in determining its relevance. Most key information should be included in the first one or two sentences as they tend to be used by research engines. It may include references to publicly available papers or reports that elucidate the dataset or provide useful links to webpages.

Partners completing metadata should ensure that this is of high-quality enabling users in future to find a dataset and determine if they wish to use it. Metadata must include a good explanatory title and an accurate concise description (e.g. what, where, when, how, why, who).

What: *Provides a concise description of what has been recorded and the format of the data. It aims to immediately inform the reader about the nature of the resource.*

Where: *Indicate the spatial coverage of the data.*

When: *The timeframe during which the data was collected, providing clarity on the temporal scope of the dataset.*

How: *A brief overview of the methodology used in data collection.*

Why: *The purpose behind data collection and the potential users who may find the data valuable.*

Who: *The parties responsible for collecting and interpreting the data are identified in this section.*

Key words.

Please add a set of keywords to make your data more easily findable.

Datasets generated will be INSPIRE compliant, with full metadata conforming to Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and DOI (Digital Object Identifiers) where appropriate. Metadata containing details of the dataset will be captured in a standardised discovery metadata format which complies with ISO standard 19115. The Research Data Alliance provides a Metadata Standards Directory (<http://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/>)
